

1 Term rewriting characterisation of LOGSPACE for 2 finite and infinite data

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6 — Abstract —

7 We show that LOGSPACE is characterised by finite orthogonal tail-recursive cons-free construc-
8 tor term rewriting systems, contributing to a line of research initiated by Neil Jones. We de-
9 scribe a LOGSPACE algorithm which computes constructor normal forms. This algorithm is
10 used in the proof of our main result: that simple stream term rewriting systems characterise
11 LOGSPACE-computable stream functions as defined by Ramyaa and Leivant. This result con-
12 cerns characterising logarithmic-space computation on infinite streams by means of infinitary
13 rewriting.

14 **2012 ACM Subject Classification** Theory of computation → Complexity theory and logic, The-
15 ory of computation → Equational logic and rewriting

16 **Keywords and phrases** LOGSPACE, implicit complexity, term rewriting, infinitary rewriting,
17 streams

18 **Digital Object Identifier** 10.4230/LIPIcs.FSCD.2018.13

19 **1** Introduction

20 The goal of the field of implicit computational complexity is to characterise computational
21 complexity classes without reference to external measuring conditions. One of the first
22 such implicit characterisations was that of LOGSPACE as the class of problems which
23 can be decided by deterministic two-way multihead finite automata [6]. Inspired by this
24 well-known characterisation, Neil Jones gave new characterisations of this class as “cons-
25 free” tail-recursive programs in several formalisms [9, 7, 8]. In cons-free programs data
26 constructors cannot occur in function bodies. Put differently, cons-free programs are read-
27 only: recursive data can only be read from input, but not created or altered (except
28 taking subterms). Cons-free programming was subsequently used to characterise a variety of
29 complexity classes [9, 7, 8, 2, 3, 10, 11, 12].

30 In this paper we extend the cons-free approach to computation on infinite streams.
31 In [14, 13] Ramyaa and Leivant define the class of LOGSPACE-computable stream functions
32 and show that it is characterised by ramified corecurrence in two tiers. Our main contribution
33 is a cons-free infinitary term-rewriting characterisation of this class. We show that a stream
34 function is computable in LOGSPACE, in the sense of Ramyaa and Leivant, if and only if it
35 is definable in a simple stream TRS. As an intermediate step, we also give infinitary rewriting
36 characterisations of stream functions computable by (jumping) finite stream transducers.

37 In order to obtain our characterisation of LOGSPACE-computability on streams, we give
38 an algorithm to compute the (finite) constructor normal form of a (finite) term of a certain

¹ Supported by the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement number 704111.

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3rd International Conference on Formal Structures for Computation and Deduction (FSCD 2018).

Editor: Hélène Kirchner; Article No. 13; pp. 13:1–13:20

Leibniz International Proceedings in Informatics

LIPICs Schloss Dagstuhl – Leibniz-Zentrum für Informatik, Dagstuhl Publishing, Germany

39 form in a finite orthogonal tail-recursive cons-free constructor TRS. Using this algorithm we
 40 obtain a term rewriting characterisation of LOGSPACE (in the ordinary finite sense).

41 In previous work [9, 8, 2] LOGSPACE was characterised by tail-recursive cons-free
 42 programs. The idea to transpose characterisations obtained via cons-free programs into the
 43 formalism of TRSs has already been exploited to characterise other complexity classes in [3,
 44 11, 10], but there orthogonality was not assumed. Our method of introducing \perp -reductions
 45 may be seen as a degenerate case of the method in [3] (see also [10]), but the algorithm used
 46 there to compute constructor normal forms in polynomial time is fundamentally different
 47 from ours and does not easily adapt to logarithmic space computation. In the first part of
 48 this paper, the main novelty is a trick to detect looping in logarithmic space, and using this
 49 to obtain a LOGSPACE algorithm for computing constructor normal forms.

50 2 Term rewriting systems

51 We assume familiarity with term rewriting [1]. In this short section we fix the notation and
 52 briefly recall some definitions.

53 ► **Definition 2.1.** A *term rewriting system* (TRS) is a set of *rules* of the form $l \rightarrow r$ where
 54 l, r are terms and l is not a variable and $\text{Var}(r) \subseteq \text{Var}(l)$, where $\text{Var}(t)$ denotes the variables
 55 occurring in t . Given a TRS R , the reduction relation \rightarrow_R is the compatible closure of the
 56 contraction relation $\{(\sigma l, \sigma r) \mid l \rightarrow r \in R, \sigma \text{ a substitution}\}$. We use \rightarrow^* for the transitive-
 57 reflexive closure of \rightarrow , and $\rightarrow^=$ for the reflexive closure, and \Rightarrow for the parallel closure. For
 58 precise definitions see [1]. In particular, \Rightarrow is reflexive.

59 A *defined symbol* in a TRS R is a function symbol which occurs at the root of a left-hand
 60 side of a rule in R . A *constructor symbol* in a TRS R is a function symbol which is not a
 61 defined symbol in R . A *constructor term* is a term which does not contain defined function
 62 symbols (it may contain variables). A *constructor normal form* is a constructor term which
 63 does not contain variables (so it contains only constructors). A *constructor head normal*
 64 *form* (chnf) is a term of the form $c(t_1, \dots, t_n)$ with c a constructor. A *constructor TRS* is
 65 a TRS R such that for $l \rightarrow r \in R$ we have $l = f(l_1, \dots, l_n)$ where l_1, \dots, l_n are constructor
 66 terms.

67 A redex is *innermost* if it does not contain other redexes. A reduction step is innermost
 68 if it contracts an innermost redex.

69 A *decision problem* is a set of binary words $A \subseteq \{0, 1\}^*$. Assuming the signature contains
 70 the constants $0, 1, \text{nil}$ and a binary constructor symbol cons , every $w \in \{0, 1\}^*$ may be
 71 represented by a term \bar{w} in an obvious way. A TRS R *accepts* a decision problem A if there
 72 is a function symbol f such that for every $w \in \{0, 1\}^*$ we have: $f(\bar{w}) \rightarrow_R^* 1$ iff $w \in A$.

73 3 LOGSPACE for finite data

74 In this section we show that finite orthogonal tail-recursive cons-free constructor TRSs
 75 characterise LOGSPACE, i.e., a decision problem is in LOGSPACE iff it is accepted by a
 76 finite orthogonal tail-recursive cons-free constructor TRS. As part of the proof we give an
 77 algorithm which computes the constructor normal form of a term of a certain form, if there
 78 exists one, or rejects otherwise. This algorithm will also be used in Section 6.

79 ► **Definition 3.1.** A constructor TRS R is *cons-free* if for each $l \rightarrow r \in R$ every chnf subterm
 80 of r either occurs in l or is a constructor normal form. A constructor TRS R is *tail-recursive* if
 81 there is a preorder \succsim on defined function symbols such that for every $f(u_1, \dots, u_n) \rightarrow r \in R$
 82 and every defined function symbol g the following hold:

- 83 ■ if $r = g(t_1, \dots, t_k)$ then $f \gtrsim g$,
 - 84 ■ if $g(t_1, \dots, t_k)$ is a proper subterm of r then $f > g$.
- 85 A TRS is *strictly tail-recursive* if it is tail-recursive and each right-hand side of a rule contains
 86 at most one defined function symbol.

87 For terms t_1, \dots, t_n by $\mathcal{B}(t_1, \dots, t_n)$ we denote the sets of all constructor normal forms
 88 occurring either in one of t_i or in a right-hand side of a rule of R . Note that $\mathcal{B}(t_1, \dots, t_n)$ is
 89 finite if R is.

90 Our definition of tail-recursive is based on standard definitions in the literature [8, 2],
 91 adapted to the term rewriting framework.

92 ► **Proposition 3.2.** *Any problem decidable in LOGSPACE is accepted by a finite orthogonal*
 93 *tail-recursive cons-free constructor TRS.*

94 **Proof.** This is a straightforward adaptation of previous work [7, 2]. One may e.g. easily
 95 encode any $\text{CM}^{\wedge+}$ program from [7] by a finite orthogonal strictly tail-recursive cons-free
 96 constructor TRS. Because the obtained TRS is orthogonal and strictly tail-recursive, the
 97 reduction strategy does not play a significant role. We skip the routine details. ◀

98 It is more difficult to show the other direction of the characterisation result, i.e., that any
 99 decision problem accepted by a finite orthogonal tail-recursive cons-free constructor TRS is
 100 in LOGSPACE. Indeed, if the TRS is tail-recursive but not strictly tail-recursive, then terms
 101 which have a constructor normal form may also have arbitrarily large reducts. Consider
 102 e.g. the following TRS R :

$$103 \quad f(x) \rightarrow_R f(g(x)) \quad h(x) \rightarrow_R a$$

104 Then $h(f(a)) \rightarrow_R a$ but also $h(f(a)) \rightarrow_R^* h(f(g^n(a)))$ for any $n \in \mathbb{N}$. This example also
 105 shows that the innermost strategy may fail to give a normal form even if a term has one.

106 We will show that a constructor normal form may always be reached by an eager $R\perp$ -
 107 reduction, denoted $\rightarrow_{R\perp}^*$, which contracts only innermost R -redexes and eagerly (as soon
 108 as possible) replaces by \perp an innermost subterm with no constructor normal form in R .
 109 For instance, in the example TRS R given above $h(f(a)) \rightarrow_{\perp} h(\perp) \rightarrow_R a$ is an eager
 110 $R\perp$ -reduction, but $h(f(a)) \rightarrow_R h(f^2(a))$ is not. The term $f(a)$ does not have a constructor
 111 normal form in R , so it *cannot* be R -contracted in an eager $R\perp$ -reduction – it *must* be
 112 contracted to \perp .

113 Whether a subterm has a constructor normal form in R may be decided using a constant
 114 number of logarithmic counters. An eager $R\perp$ -reduction has the form

$$115 \quad f_1(w_1^1, \dots, w_{n_1}^1) \rightarrow_{R\perp}^* f_1(t_1^1, \dots, t_{n_1}^1) \rightarrow_R^\epsilon f_2(w_1^2, \dots, w_{n_2}^2) \rightarrow_{R\perp}^* f_2(t_1^2, \dots, t_{n_2}^2) \rightarrow_R^\epsilon \dots$$

116 where t_i^j is the constructor normal form w.r.t. eager $R\perp$ -reduction of w_i^j (\perp is considered to
 117 be a constructor) and $f_i \gtrsim f_j$ for $i \leq j$. At some point either we reach a constructor normal
 118 form or a term $f_i(t_1^i, \dots, t_{n_i}^i)$ repeats. Because of cons-freeness, there are only polynomially
 119 many such terms. Hence, a logarithmic counter may be used to detect looping. Because of
 120 tail-recursive, computing the constructor normal form (w.r.t. eager $R\perp$ -reduction) t_i^j
 121 of w_i^j may be done by a recursive invocation, and the recursion depth will be constant. The
 122 rest of this section is devoted to making the above arguments precise.

123 ► **Definition 3.3.** Let R be a constructor TRS and let \perp be a fresh constant, i.e., not
 124 occurring in any of the rules of R . We define the \perp -contraction relation $\rightarrow_{\perp}^\epsilon$ by: $t \rightarrow_{\perp}^\epsilon \perp$
 125 if t does not R -reduce to a constructor normal form. The \perp -reduction relation \rightarrow_{\perp} is the

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126 compatible closure of $\rightarrow_{\perp}^{\epsilon}$. We set $\rightarrow_{R\perp} = \rightarrow_R \cup \rightarrow_{\perp}$. An $R\perp$ -reduction is *eager* if only
 127 innermost $R\perp$ -redexes are contracted and priority is given to \perp -reduction, i.e., an R -redex t
 128 such that $t \rightarrow_{\perp} \perp$ is not R -contracted in the reduction. We use $\rightarrow_{R\perp e}$ for an eager one-step
 129 $R\perp$ -reduction.

130 Note that \perp is a constructor. So a term of the form $c(t_1, \dots, t_n)$ with c a constructor never
 131 eagerly $R\perp$ -reduces to \perp , because if it does not have a constructor normal form in R then
 132 there is a $R\perp$ -redex in one of the t_i . Note that a term is in normal form w.r.t. $R\perp$ -reduction
 133 iff it is a constructor normal form.

134 We first show that in a left-linear constructor TRS \perp -reduction may be postponed after
 135 R -reduction. This will imply that eager $R\perp$ -reduction to a constructor normal form not
 136 containing \perp may be replaced with R -reduction.

137 ► **Lemma 3.4.** *In a left-linear constructor TRS, if $u \rightrightarrows_{\perp} t \rightarrow_R t'$ then there is u' with*
 138 *$u \rightarrow_R u' \rightrightarrows_{\perp} t'$.*

139 **Proof.** Without loss of generality we may assume that $t \rightarrow_R t'$ occurs at the root by a rule
 140 $l \rightarrow r$ with substitution σ . By the choice of \perp the term l does not contain \perp . We have
 141 $t = \sigma(l)$. So \perp in t may occur only below a variable position of l . Since \perp are the contracta
 142 in $u \rightrightarrows_{\perp} t$, the expansions $u \rightrightarrows_{\perp} t$ in t occur below variable positions of l . Hence, there is σ'
 143 such that $\sigma'(x) \rightrightarrows_{\perp} \sigma(x)$ for all $x \in \text{Var}(l)$ and $u = \sigma'(l)$. Then take $u' = \sigma'(r)$. ◀

144 ► **Corollary 3.5.** *In a left-linear constructor TRS, if $t \rightarrow_{R\perp}^* t'$ then there is u with $t \rightarrow_R^*$
 145 $u \rightarrow_{\perp}^* t'$.*

146 ► **Lemma 3.6.** *In a left-linear constructor TRS, if $t \rightarrow_{R\perp}^* s$ with s a constructor normal
 147 form not containing \perp , then $t \rightarrow_R^* s$.*

148 **Proof.** Induction on the number n of \perp -contractions in $t \rightarrow_{R\perp}^* s$. If $n > 0$ then consider the
 149 last \perp -contraction: $t \rightarrow_{R\perp}^* t' \rightarrow_{\perp} t'' \rightarrow_R^* s$. By Lemma 3.4 there is s' with $t' \rightarrow_R^* s' \rightrightarrows_{\perp} s$.
 150 Because s does not contain \perp , we have $s' = s$. So $t \rightarrow_{R\perp}^* s$ with $n - 1$ \perp -contractions. Hence
 151 $t \rightarrow_R^* s$ by the inductive hypothesis. ◀

152 The following lemma shows that eager $R\perp$ -reduction in $\sigma(t)$, with t a linear constructor
 153 term, occurs below variable positions.

154 ► **Lemma 3.7.** *In a constructor TRS R , if t is a linear constructor term and $\sigma(t) \rightarrow_{R\perp e}^* t'$
 155 then there is σ' such that $t' = \sigma'(t)$ and $\sigma(x) \rightarrow_{R\perp e}^* \sigma'(x)$ for all $x \in \text{Var}(t)$.*

156 **Proof.** Induction on t . If $t = x$ then take $\sigma'(x) = t'$. Otherwise $t = c(t_1, \dots, t_n)$ and
 157 $t' = c(t'_1, \dots, t'_n)$ with $\sigma(t_i) \rightarrow_{R\perp e}^* t'_i$ and c a constructor. By the inductive hypothesis for
 158 $i = 1, \dots, n$ there is σ'_i with $\sigma'_i(t_i) = t'_i$ and $\sigma(x) \rightarrow_{R\perp e}^* \sigma'_i(x)$ for $x \in \text{Var}(t_i)$. Because t is
 159 linear, $\text{Var}(t_i) \cap \text{Var}(t_j) = \emptyset$ for $i \neq j$. So the σ'_i s may be combined into a single substitution σ'
 160 with the required properties. ◀

161 ► **Corollary 3.8.** *In a left-linear constructor TRS R , if $f(t_1, \dots, t_n) \rightarrow_R^{\epsilon} t$ and $t_i \rightarrow_{R\perp e}^* t'_i$
 162 for $i = 1, \dots, n$, then there is t' with $f(t'_1, \dots, t'_n) \rightarrow_R^{\epsilon} t' \xrightarrow{*}_{R\perp e} t$. Moreover, the contraction
 163 $f(t'_1, \dots, t'_n) \rightarrow_R^{\epsilon} t'$ is by the same rule as $f(t_1, \dots, t_n) \rightarrow_R^{\epsilon} t$.*

164 **Proof.** Assume $f(t_1, \dots, t_n) \rightarrow_R^{\epsilon} t$ by a rule $f(l_1, \dots, l_n) \rightarrow r$ with substitution σ . Because
 165 each l_i is a linear constructor term and $\text{Var}(l_i) \cap \text{Var}(l_j) = \emptyset$ for $i \neq j$, by Lemma 3.7
 166 there is σ' such that for $i = 1, \dots, n$ we have $\sigma'(l_i) = t'_i$ and $\sigma(x) \rightarrow_{R\perp e}^* \sigma'(x)$. Thus $u =$
 167 $f(\sigma'(l_1), \dots, \sigma'(l_n)) \rightarrow_R \sigma'(r)$. Also $t' = \sigma(r) \rightarrow_{R\perp e}^* \sigma'(r)$, because $\text{Var}(r) \subseteq \text{Var}(l_1, \dots, l_n)$.
 168 So we may take $t' = \sigma'(r)$. ◀

169 The next lemma shows a strengthening of the diamond property for eager $R\perp$ -reduction
170 in orthogonal TRSs.

171 ► **Lemma 3.9.** *In an orthogonal TRS R , if $t \rightarrow_{R\perp e} t_1$ and $t \rightarrow_{R\perp e} t_2$ then either $t_1 = t_2$ or
172 there is t' with $t_1 \rightarrow_{R\perp e} t'$ and $t_2 \rightarrow_{R\perp e} t'$.*

173 **Proof.** If the redexes are parallel then the second part of the disjunction holds. Because both
174 redexes are innermost, if they are not parallel we may assume without loss of generality that
175 both of them are at the root. If both of them are R -redexes, then $t_1 = t_2$ by orthogonality.
176 If both are \perp -redexes then $t_1 = t_2 = \perp$. It is not possible that one redex is a \perp -redex and
177 the other an R -redex, because the reductions are eager. ◀

178 The following simple lemma is needed in the proof of Lemma 3.11.

179 ► **Lemma 3.10.** *In a cons-free constructor TRS, if every subterm of t in chnf is in constructor
180 normal form and $t \rightarrow_R^* t'$ and t' is in chnf, then t' is in constructor normal form.*

181 **Proof.** Because the TRS is cons-free, any chnf subterm of any R -reduct of t must be in $\mathcal{B}(t)$.
182 More precisely, one shows that if $t \rightarrow_R u$ then still every subterm of u in chnf is in constructor
183 normal form. ◀

184 *In the rest of this section we assume that R is a finite orthogonal tail-recursive cons-free
185 constructor TRS.*

186 Note that because R is finite and tail-recursive the partial order on the equivalence classes
187 determined by \succsim may be extended to a well order $>_E$. We write $t_1 >_E t_2$ ($t_1 \geq_E t_2$) if the
188 greatest equivalence class of a defined function symbol in t_1 is greater (greater or equal) than
189 the greatest equivalence class of a defined function symbol in t_2 . We write $f \leq_E t$ if the
190 equivalence class of the defined function symbol f is less or equal to the greatest equivalence
191 class of a defined function symbol in t . Note that if $t \rightarrow_{R\perp}^* t'$ then $t \geq_E t'$, because R is
192 tail-recursive.

193 Our next goal is to show that every term has a constructor normal form (possibly
194 containing \perp) reachable by eager $R\perp$ -reduction. This will imply that eager $R\perp$ -reduction
195 commutes with R -reduction, and that eager $R\perp$ -reduction is terminating.

196 ► **Lemma 3.11.** *Assume that for all t' with $t' \leq_E t$ there is s in constructor normal form
197 such that $t' \rightarrow_{R\perp e}^* s$. If $t' \xrightarrow{R} t \rightarrow_{R\perp e} u$ then there is u' with $t' \rightarrow_{R\perp e}^* u' \xrightarrow{R} u$.*

198 **Proof.** Note that because the redex contracted in $t \rightarrow_{R\perp e} u$ is innermost, it cannot happen
199 that the redex contracted in $t \rightarrow_R t'$ occurs strictly inside this redex. So we may assume
200 without loss of generality that the redex contracted in $t \rightarrow_R t'$ occurs at the root.

201 If $u = \perp$ then $t = f(s_1, \dots, s_n)$ with s_1, \dots, s_n in constructor normal form, because the
202 $R\perp$ -reduction is innermost. Since $t' \leq_E t$, there is a constructor normal form s such that
203 $t' \rightarrow_{R\perp e}^* s$. If $s = \perp$ then we may take $u' = \perp$. Otherwise, $s = c(s'_1, \dots, s'_m)$ with $c \neq \perp$ a
204 constructor. By Corollary 3.5 there is w with $t \rightarrow_R t' \rightarrow_R^* w \rightarrow_{\perp}^* s$. Then w is in chnf. But
205 then by Lemma 3.10 it is in constructor normal form. This contradicts $t \rightarrow_{\perp} \perp$.

206 If $t \rightarrow_{R\perp e} u$ contracts an R -redex at the root, then $u = t'$ because R is orthogonal, so
207 take $u' = t'$. The remaining case, when the eager $R\perp$ -contraction occurs strictly below the
208 root, follows from Corollary 3.8. ◀

209 ► **Lemma 3.12.** *Assume that for all t with $t <_E g$ there is s in constructor normal form such
210 that $t \rightarrow_{R\perp e}^* s$. If $g(t_1, \dots, t_n) \rightarrow_R^* s$ with g a defined function symbol and s in constructor
211 normal form and $t_i <_E g$ and $t_i \rightarrow_{R\perp e}^* w_i$ for $i = 1, \dots, n$, then $g(w_1, \dots, w_n) \rightarrow_R^* s$.*

212 **Proof.** Induction on the number of root steps in $g(t_1, \dots, t_n) \rightarrow_R^* s$. There is at least one
 213 root step, so $g(t_1, \dots, t_n) \rightarrow_R^* g(t'_1, \dots, t'_n) \rightarrow_R^\epsilon t \rightarrow_R^* s$ and, because R is cons-free and
 214 tail-recursive, either $t = s$ or $t = g'(u_1, \dots, u_m)$ with $g' \leq_E g$ and $u_i <_E g$. By Lemma 3.11
 215 there are w'_1, \dots, w'_n such that $w_i \rightarrow_R^* w'_i$ and $t'_i \rightarrow_{R \perp e}^* w'_i$ for $i = 1, \dots, n$. By Corollary 3.8
 216 there is t' with $g(w'_1, \dots, w'_n) \rightarrow_R^\epsilon t'$ and $t \rightarrow_{R \perp e}^* t'$. If $t = s$ then $t' = s$ and we are
 217 done. Otherwise, by Corollary 3.8, $t' = g'(u'_1, \dots, u'_m)$ and $u_i \rightarrow_{R \perp e}^* u'_i$. By the inductive
 218 hypothesis $t' \rightarrow_R^* s$. Hence $g(w_1, \dots, w_n) \rightarrow_R^* g(w'_1, \dots, w'_n) \rightarrow_R t' \rightarrow_R^* s$. ◀

219 ▶ **Lemma 3.13.** *Assume that for all t with $t <_E g$ there is s in constructor normal form such
 220 that $t \rightarrow_{R \perp e}^* s$. If $g(t_1, \dots, t_n) \rightarrow_R^* s$ with g a defined function symbol and s in constructor
 221 normal form and $t_i <_E g$ for $i = 1, \dots, n$, then $g(t_1, \dots, t_n) \rightarrow_{R \perp e}^* s$.*

222 **Proof.** The reduction $g(t_1, \dots, t_n) \rightarrow_R^* s$ has the form:

$$223 \quad g(t_1, \dots, t_n) \rightarrow_R^* g(u_1, \dots, u_n) \rightarrow_R^\epsilon g_1(t_1^1, \dots, t_{n_1}^1) \rightarrow_R^* g_1(u_1^1, \dots, u_{n_1}^1) \rightarrow_R^\epsilon \dots \rightarrow_R^\epsilon s.$$

224 We proceed by induction on the number of root steps in this R -reduction. Since $t_i <_E g$
 225 for $i = 1, \dots, n$, there are s_1, \dots, s_n in constructor normal form such that $t_i \rightarrow_{R \perp e}^* s_i$. By
 226 Lemma 3.11 we also have $u_i \rightarrow_{R \perp e}^* s_i$. By Corollary 3.8 there is t' with $g(s_1, \dots, s_n) \rightarrow_R^\epsilon t'$ and
 227 either $t' = s$, or $t' = g_1(w_1, \dots, w_{n_1})$ and $t_i^1 \rightarrow_{R \perp e}^* w_i$. We have $g(s_1, \dots, s_n) \rightarrow_{R \perp e} s$ because
 228 the R -reduction to t' is innermost and $g(s_1, \dots, s_n) \rightarrow_R^* s$ by Lemma 3.12. Hence if $t' = s$ then
 229 $g(t_1, \dots, t_n) \rightarrow_{R \perp e}^* s$. So assume $t' = g_1(w_1, \dots, w_{n_1})$ with $t_i^1 \rightarrow_{R \perp e}^* w_i$. By the inductive
 230 hypothesis $g_1(t_1^1, \dots, t_{n_1}^1) \rightarrow_{R \perp e}^* s$. By Lemma 3.9 we obtain $g_1(w_1, \dots, w_{n_1}) \rightarrow_{R \perp e}^* s$. Thus
 231 $g(t_1, \dots, t_n) \rightarrow_{R \perp e}^* g(s_1, \dots, s_n) \rightarrow_{R \perp e} g_1(w_1, \dots, w_{n_1}) \rightarrow_{R \perp e}^* s$. ◀

232 ▶ **Lemma 3.14.** *For every term t there exists s in constructor normal form² such that
 233 $t \rightarrow_{R \perp e}^* s$.*

234 **Proof.** We proceed by induction on pairs $\langle e, n \rangle$ ordered lexicographically, where e is the
 235 greatest, w.r.t. $>_E$, equivalence class of a defined function symbol in t , and n is the size
 236 of t . This is obvious if t is a variable. So assume $t = f(t_1, \dots, t_n)$. Since each t_k is smaller
 237 than t , by the inductive hypothesis for each $k = 1, \dots, n$ there is a constructor normal
 238 form s_k with $t_k \rightarrow_{R \perp e}^* s_k$. If f is a constructor then we are done, so assume it is a defined
 239 function symbol. If $f(s_1, \dots, s_n)$ does not R -reduce to a constructor normal form, then
 240 $f(s_1, \dots, s_n) \rightarrow_{R \perp e} \perp$, so we may take $s = \perp$. Otherwise $f(s_1, \dots, s_n) \rightarrow_R^* s$ for some s in
 241 constructor normal form. Of course, $f \leq_E t$, so the inductive hypothesis implies that for
 242 all t' with $t' <_E f$ there is s' in constructor normal form such that $t' \rightarrow_{R \perp e}^* s'$. Thus by
 243 Lemma 3.13: $t \rightarrow_{R \perp e}^* f(s_1, \dots, s_n) \rightarrow_{R \perp e}^* s$. ◀

244 ▶ **Corollary 3.15.** *If $t' \stackrel{*}{R} \leftarrow t \rightarrow_{R \perp e}^* u$ then there is u' with $t' \rightarrow_{R \perp e}^* u' \stackrel{*}{R} \leftarrow u$.*

245 **Proof.** Follows from Lemma 3.11 and Lemma 3.14. ◀

246 ▶ **Remark.** Corollary 3.15 fails if the $R \perp$ -reduction is not required to be eager (though
 247 innermost would suffice). Consider the TRS R :

$$248 \quad f(x) \rightarrow_R f(x) \quad g(c(x)) \rightarrow_R a$$

249 We have $g(c(f(x))) \rightarrow_R a$, but also $g(c(f(x))) \rightarrow_{\perp} g(\perp) \rightarrow_{\perp} \perp$, because $c(f(x))$ does not
 250 R -reduce to a constructor normal form.

² Recall that \perp is considered to be a constructor.

251 The corollary also fails if R is not required to be cons-free. Consider the TRS R :

$$252 \quad f(x) \rightarrow_R f(x) \quad g(x) \rightarrow_R c(f(x))$$

253 Then $g(x) \rightarrow_{R\perp e}^* \perp$. On the other hand $g(x) \rightarrow_R c(f(x))$ and $c(f(x)) \not\rightarrow_{R\perp e}^* \perp$.

254 If R is not required to be tail-recursive then this also fails. Consider the TRS R :

$$255 \quad h(x) \rightarrow_R h(f(x)) \quad f(x) \rightarrow_R g(x, f(x)) \quad g(x, y) \rightarrow_R x$$

256 Then $h(a) \rightarrow_{R\perp e} \perp$, because $h(t)$ does not have a constructor normal form for any t . Also
 257 $h(a) \rightarrow_R h(f(a))$. The term $h(f(a))$ has no constructor normal form, but $h(f(a)) \not\rightarrow_{R\perp e} \perp$
 258 because the \perp -redex is not innermost. And there is no constructor normal form s with
 259 $f(a) \rightarrow_{R\perp e}^* s$ (note that $f(a) \rightarrow_R g(a, f(a)) \rightarrow_R a$ but the reduction is not innermost).
 260 Hence, there is no eager $R\perp$ -reduction from $h(f(a))$ to \perp .

261 The proof of the next lemma is an adaptation of the standard argument that in an
 262 orthogonal TRS if a term is weakly innermost normalising then it is innermost terminating.

263 ► **Lemma 3.16.** *Eager $R\perp$ -reduction is terminating.*

264 **Proof.** Follows from Lemma 3.14 and Lemma 3.9. Assume there is an infinite eager $R\perp$ -
 265 reduction $t_0 \rightarrow_{R\perp e} t_1 \rightarrow_{R\perp e} t_2 \rightarrow_{R\perp e} \dots$. By Lemma 3.14 there is u in constructor normal
 266 form with $t_0 \rightarrow_{R\perp e}^* u$. Using Lemma 3.9 one shows by induction on the length of $t_0 \rightarrow_{R\perp e}^* u$
 267 that there is an infinite eager $R\perp$ -reduction starting at u . This contradicts that u is a
 268 constructor normal form. ◀

269 Termination of eager $R\perp$ -reduction is crucial in justifying the correctness of the algorithm
 270 described in the proof of the following theorem.

271 ► **Proposition 3.17.** *Let R be a finite orthogonal tail-recursive cons-free constructor TRS.
 272 There is a LOGSPACE algorithm which given a term $t = f(t_1, \dots, t_n)$, with t_1, \dots, t_n in
 273 constructor normal form (possibly containing \perp), computes the constructor normal form $s \in$
 274 $\mathcal{B}(t, \perp)$ such that $t \rightarrow_{R\perp e}^* s$.*

275 **Proof.** Note that because R is cons-free, if $t \rightarrow_{R\perp e}^* t'$ then any subterm of t' with a constructor
 276 symbol at the root is in $\mathcal{B}(t, \perp)$. Because the size of $\mathcal{B}(t, \perp)$ is polynomial (there is only a
 277 constant number of constructor normal forms occurring in right-hand sides of rules in R),
 278 constructor normal forms occurring in $R\perp$ -reducts of t may be represented using a logarithmic
 279 number of bits.

280 Because R is a tail-recursive constructor TRS, $f(t_1, \dots, t_n)$ either is R -irreducible, in
 281 which case it may be contracted to \perp , or it R -contracts (eagerly) to a constructor normal
 282 form, or it R -contracts (not necessarily eagerly) to a term $f'(t'_1, \dots, t'_m)$ where f' is a defined
 283 function symbol and $f \succ f'$ and for each defined function symbol g in one of t'_1, \dots, t'_m we
 284 have $f > g$. Apply the procedure recursively, in depth-first order, to subterms of t'_1, \dots, t'_m of
 285 the form $g(u_1, \dots, u_k)$ with g a defined function symbol and u_1, \dots, u_k in constructor normal
 286 form. This results in s_1, \dots, s_m in constructor normal form such that $t'_k \rightarrow_{R\perp e}^* s_k$. Note
 287 that the number of defined function symbols in t'_1, \dots, t'_m is constant and depends only on
 288 the rule of R applied to t . Hence only logarithmic space is needed to store (representations
 289 of) intermediate results. Note also that $f > g$ for g a defined symbol in t'_1, \dots, t'_m , which
 290 guarantees termination of the recursion.

291 So $f(t_1, \dots, t_n) \rightarrow_R^\epsilon f'(t'_1, \dots, t'_m) \rightarrow_{R\perp e}^* f'(s_1, \dots, s_m)$ with s_1, \dots, s_m again in construc-
 292 tor normal form. We keep repeating the steps described in the previous paragraph, starting

293 with $f'(s_1, \dots, s_m)$ now, until we reach a constructor normal form or we detect looping in
 294 which case \perp is returned. Looping detection may be realised using a single counter with
 295 a logarithmic number of bits. Indeed, by repeating the steps described in the previous
 296 paragraph we obtain a reduction of the form

$$297 \quad t \rightarrow_R^\epsilon f_1(w_1^1, \dots, w_{n_1}^1) \rightarrow_{R\perp e}^* f_1(t_1^1, \dots, t_{n_1}^1) \rightarrow_R^\epsilon f_2(w_1^2, \dots, w_{n_2}^2) \rightarrow_{R\perp e}^* f_2(t_1^2, \dots, t_{n_2}^2) \rightarrow_R^\epsilon \dots$$

298 where the $R\perp e$ -reductions occur strictly below the root. Let M be the maximum arity
 299 of a defined function symbol in R , and K the number of defined function symbols in R ,
 300 and N the size of $\mathcal{B}(t)$ (note that N is bounded by the size of t plus a constant). There
 301 are at most N different constructor normal forms occurring in the $R\perp$ -reducts of t , so if
 302 the above reduction contains more than KN^M root steps, then one of the root R -redexes
 303 $f_i(t_1^i, \dots, t_{n_i}^i)$ must repeat. So we keep a counter and return \perp after performing KN^M
 304 root steps if we do not stop with a constructor normal form earlier. To see that this is
 305 correct, note that if a root redex repeats then an infinite reduction of the above form may be
 306 constructed. Assume $t \rightarrow_R^* s$ for a constructor normal form s . Then the initial R -contraction
 307 $t \rightarrow_R^\epsilon f_1(w_1^1, \dots, w_{n_1}^1)$ is eager, so $t \rightarrow_{R\perp e}^* f_1(t_1^1, \dots, t_{n_1}^1)$, and thus $f_1(t_1^1, \dots, t_{n_1}^1) \rightarrow_R^* s$ by
 308 Corollary 3.15. By induction on k we show that $f_k(t_1^k, \dots, t_{n_k}^k) \rightarrow_R^* s$ and each of the root
 309 R -contractions $f_k(t_1^k, \dots, t_{n_k}^k) \rightarrow_R^\epsilon f_{k+1}(w_1^{k+1}, \dots, w_{n_{k+1}}^{k+1})$ is eager, i.e.

$$310 \quad t \rightarrow_{R\perp e}^+ f_1(t_1^1, \dots, t_{n_1}^1) \rightarrow_{R\perp e}^+ f_2(t_1^2, \dots, t_{n_2}^2) \rightarrow_{R\perp e}^+ f_3(t_1^3, \dots, t_{n_3}^3) \rightarrow_{R\perp e}^+ \dots$$

311 Hence, there exists an infinite eager $R\perp$ -reduction from t , which contradicts Lemma 3.16.
 312 Thus, if a root redex repeats then $t \rightarrow_{\perp} \perp$. So returning \perp is correct in this case.

313 The above algorithm terminates and the recursion depth (the maximum nesting of
 314 recursive calls) is constant, because in the recursive calls for subterms of t'_1, \dots, t'_m the
 315 defined function symbol at the root is strictly smaller in the preorder \succsim . Also note that in
 316 each recursive call on a subterm $g(u_1, \dots, u_n)$ of one of t'_1, \dots, t'_m the constructor normal
 317 forms u_1, \dots, u_n are in $\mathcal{B}(t, \perp)$, because then $g(u_1, \dots, u_n)$ is a subterm of an $R\perp$ -reduct
 318 of t . So u_1, \dots, u_n may still be represented in logarithmic space. Hence, at each recursive
 319 invocation the algorithm uses logarithmic space to store the representations of the function
 320 symbol arguments, a constant number of logarithmic-space variables to store the intermediate
 321 results of recursive calls, and a logarithmic counter to detect looping. Since the recursion
 322 depth is constant, the algorithm altogether uses logarithmic space. \blacktriangleleft

323 **► Theorem 3.18.** *A decision problem is in LOGSPACE iff it is accepted by a finite orthogonal*
 324 *tail-recursive cons-free constructor TRS.*

325 **Proof.** The direction from left to right follows from Proposition 3.2. For the other direction
 326 it suffices to show an algorithm which given a finite orthogonal tail-recursive cons-free
 327 constructor TRS R and a term $t = f(t_1, \dots, t_n)$ with t_1, \dots, t_n in constructor normal form
 328 not containing \perp , computes in LOGSPACE the constructor normal form of t , if it has one,
 329 or rejects otherwise. The algorithm is to run the procedure from Proposition 3.17 to find a
 330 constructor normal form s with $t \rightarrow_{R\perp e}^* s$. If s does not contain \perp then $t \rightarrow_R^* s$ by Lemma 3.6.
 331 Otherwise, t does not have a constructor normal form in R and we reject. Indeed, if $t \rightarrow_R^* s'$
 332 with s' in constructor normal form then s' does not contain \perp because t does not. But $s = s'$
 333 by Corollary 3.15. \blacktriangleleft

334 4 Stream Term Rewriting Systems

335 In this section we define stream TRSs which allow possibly infinite stream terms. We define
 336 infinitary reduction in a stream TRS which captures the notion of a “limit” of an infinite

337 reduction sequence.

338 ► **Definition 4.1.** A *stream TRS* is a two-sorted constructor TRS with sorts s (the sort of
 339 streams) and d (the sort of finite data), finitely many defined function symbols, finitely many
 340 data constructors $c_i : d^n \rightarrow d$, and one binary stream constructor $\text{cons} : d \times s \rightarrow s$. Terms of
 341 sort s are *stream terms*. Terms of sort d are *data terms*. For stream TRSs we allow terms
 342 to be infinite. We write $t_1 :: t_2$ instead of $\text{cons } t_1 t_2$. If $l \rightarrow r \in R$ is a rule, then we require
 343 that l and r have the same sort.

344 *Stream rules* are the rules $l \rightarrow r$ such that l is a stream term. *Data rules* are the rules
 345 $l \rightarrow r$ such that l is a data term. A *stream (resp. data) function symbol* is a defined function
 346 symbol of type $\tau_1 \times \dots \times \tau_n \rightarrow s$ (resp. $\tau_1 \times \dots \times \tau_n \rightarrow d$).

347 A *simple stream rule* has the form:

$$348 \quad f(u_1, \dots, u_n) \rightarrow t_1 :: \dots :: t_k :: g(w_1, \dots, w_m)$$

349 where $k \geq 0$ and we require:

- 350 1. u_1, \dots, u_n are constructor terms,
- 351 2. every stream subterm of one of $t_1, \dots, t_k, w_1, \dots, w_m$ occurs (as a subterm) in u_1, \dots, u_n ,
- 352 3. if $k = 0$ then every data subterm $c(v_1, \dots, v_j)$ of each of w_1, \dots, w_m , with $c : d^j \rightarrow d$ a
 353 data constructor, either occurs in u_1, \dots, u_n or is a constructor normal form.

354 The intuitive interpretation of the restrictions of a simple stream rule is that it is *cons-free*
 355 with respect to stream subterms, and if the rule does not produce a new stream element
 356 then it is also *cons-free* with respect to data subterms.

357 Note that by requiring u_1, \dots, u_n to be constructor terms and every stream subterm of
 358 each of $t_1, \dots, t_k, w_1, \dots, w_m$ to occur in u_1, \dots, u_n , we ensure that stream function symbols
 359 cannot occur in $t_1, \dots, t_k, w_1, \dots, w_m$, i.e., g is the only stream function symbol in the
 360 right-hand side. Hence, the only function symbols present in $t_1, \dots, t_k, w_1, \dots, w_m$ are of
 361 data sort.

362 ► **Example 4.2.** Here are some examples of simple stream rules, where x, x' are stream
 363 variables, and y is a data variable, and c is a data constructor, and h is a defined data
 364 function symbol:

$$365 \quad \begin{aligned} f(a :: x, y) &\rightarrow a :: f(x, c(y)) \\ f(a :: x, b :: x') &\rightarrow a :: b :: f(b :: x', a :: x) \\ f(a :: x) &\rightarrow a :: g(x, c(a)) \\ f(a :: x, y) &\rightarrow f(x, h(y)) \end{aligned}$$

366 Here are some non-examples:

$$367 \quad \begin{aligned} f(a :: x, y) &\rightarrow f(x, c(y)) \\ f(a :: x, b :: x') &\rightarrow a :: b :: f(g(x'), a :: x) \\ f(a :: x) &\rightarrow a :: g(b :: x, c(a)) \\ f(a :: x, h(y)) &\rightarrow f(x, h(y)) \end{aligned}$$

368 ► **Definition 4.3.** Given a stream TRS R , *infinitary R-reduction* is defined coinductively.

$$369 \quad \frac{t \rightarrow_R^* t'}{t \rightarrow_R^\infty t'} \quad \frac{t \rightarrow_R^* u :: w \quad w \rightarrow_R^\infty w'}{t \rightarrow_R^\infty u :: w'}$$

13:10 Term rewriting characterisation of LOGSPACE for finite and infinite data

370 Coinductive definitions of infinitary rewriting originate from [4, 5]. Intuitively, the
 371 definition means that $t \rightarrow_R^\infty t'$ holds if this may be derived using the above rules in a
 372 possibly infinite derivation. For example, if $f(x) \rightarrow x :: f(S(x))$ is a stream rule in R , then
 373 $f(0) \rightarrow_R^\infty 0 :: S(0) :: S(S(0)) :: \dots$, i.e., $f(0)$ infinitarily reduces to an infinite stream of
 374 consecutive natural numbers.

375 The above definition differs from the standard definition of infinitary reduction via
 376 strongly convergent reduction sequences. The difference is mainly because we effectively
 377 disallow an infinitary reduction to produce an infinite nesting of defined function symbols.
 378 This eliminates the problems with confluence in infinitary rewriting. Infinitary R -reduction,
 379 defined as above, is confluent if R is finite and orthogonal. First of all, confluence holds also
 380 for finitary R -reduction.

381 ► **Lemma 4.4.** *If R is finite and orthogonal then the finitary reduction relation \rightarrow_R is*
 382 *confluent.*

383 **Proof.** Note that the terms may be infinite. But because both the left- and right-hand
 384 sides of all rules are finite, we may use virtually the same proof as in the case of ordinary
 385 orthogonal term rewriting systems, *mutatis mutandis*. ◀

386 Because of space limits we delegate the proof of confluence of infinitary reduction to
 387 Appendix A. Here we only state the result.

388 ► **Theorem 4.5.** *If R is finite and orthogonal then \rightarrow_R^∞ is confluent, i.e., if $t \rightarrow_R^\infty t_1$ and*
 389 *$t \rightarrow_R^\infty t_2$ then there exists t' such that $t_1 \rightarrow_R^\infty t'$ and $t_2 \rightarrow_R^\infty t'$.*

390 Let Σ be an alphabet. Assuming all elements of Σ are data constants in the rewriting
 391 system, each Σ -stream (infinite word in Σ^ω) may be treated as an infinite stream term.
 392 Also, finite words over Σ may be represented as stream terms in the TRS, where after the
 393 symbols representing the word there is a term with no constructor head normal form, e.g.,
 394 $a :: b :: c :: \Omega$ represents the word abc , where Ω has no chnf. Note that a stream term in
 395 chnf (Definition 2.1) has the form $u :: w$. We denote the set of terms representing finite and
 396 infinite words over Σ by $\mathcal{S}^+(\Sigma)$, and the set of terms representing infinite words by $\mathcal{S}(\Sigma)$.
 397 More precisely, the set $\mathcal{S}^+(\Sigma)$ is defined coinductively as follows.

$$398 \quad \frac{t \text{ has no chnf}}{t \in \mathcal{S}^+(\Sigma)} \quad \frac{c \in \Sigma \quad t \in \mathcal{S}^+(\Sigma)}{(c :: t) \in \mathcal{S}^+(\Sigma)}$$

399 For each term t in $\mathcal{S}^+(\Sigma)$ there is exactly one corresponding finite or infinite word $|t|$
 400 in $\Sigma^{\leq\omega} = \Sigma^\omega \cup \Sigma^*$ which this term represents.

401 ► **Lemma 4.6.** *Assume $t \rightarrow_R^\infty t'$. Then t has a chnf iff t' has a chnf.*

402 **Proof.** Follows from definitions and Lemma 4.4. ◀

403 ► **Corollary 4.7.** *Let R be a finite orthogonal stream TRS. If $t \rightarrow_R^\infty s$ and $t \rightarrow_R^\infty s'$ and*
 404 *$s, s' \in \mathcal{S}^+(\Sigma)$ then $|s| = |s'|$.*

405 ► **Definition 4.8.** A stream function $F : (\Sigma^\omega)^n \rightarrow \Sigma^{\leq\omega}$ is defined by an n -ary stream
 406 function symbol f if for any $w_1, \dots, w_n \in \Sigma^\omega$ and $s_1, \dots, s_n \in \mathcal{S}(\Sigma)$ with $|s_i| = w_i$ we
 407 have $f(s_1, \dots, s_n) \rightarrow_R^\infty s$ where $|s| = F(w_1, \dots, w_n)$. A stream function is *definable* in a
 408 stream TRS if it is defined by one of its stream function symbols.

409 A stream TRS R is *data tail-recursive* if the data rules of R form a *single-sorted* (i.e. neither
 410 left- nor right-hand sides of data rules of R contain stream subterms) finite tail-recursive
 411 cons-free constructor TRS.

412 Note that if R is data tail-recursive then data terms do not contain stream subterms,
 413 because then neither data constructors nor data function symbols can have stream arguments.
 414 In particular, if $l \rightarrow t :: r$ is a rule in R , then t does not contain stream subterms.

415 ► **Definition 4.9.** A *pure* stream TRS is a finite orthogonal stream TRS with simple stream
 416 rules, no data rules and no data constructors of arity > 0 .

417 A stream TRS has *simple data* if there exists a unary data constructor $S : d \rightarrow d$ such
 418 that for every stream rule $l \rightarrow r \in R$, if t is a data subterm of r such that $\text{Var}(t) \neq \emptyset$ then
 419 $t = S(t')$ or t is a variable.

420 A *simple* stream TRS is a finite orthogonal data tail-recursive stream TRS with simple
 421 stream rules and simple data.

422 ► **Example 4.10.** Here is an example of a simple stream TRS, where x, x' are stream variables
 423 and y, y' are data variables.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & f(x) \rightarrow g(x, x, 0, 0) \\
 & g(y :: x, x', 0, y') \rightarrow y :: g(x', x', S(y'), S(y')) \\
 & g(0 :: x, x', S(y), y') \rightarrow g(x, x', y, y') \\
 & g(1 :: x, x', S(y), y') \rightarrow g(x, x', y', y')
 \end{aligned}$$

425 In this stream TRS the stream function symbol f defines a function $F : \Sigma^\omega \rightarrow \Sigma^{\leq \omega}$ such
 426 that $F(s)$ has in position n the first element of s following a block of n consecutive 0's.

427 The following simple stream TRS defines the Thue-Morse sequence T :

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 T \rightarrow f(0) & f(x) \rightarrow h(x, x) :: f(S(x)) \\
 h(0, 0) \rightarrow 0 & \tilde{h}(0, 0) \rightarrow 1 \\
 h(0, x) \rightarrow h(x, x) & \tilde{h}(0, x) \rightarrow \tilde{h}(x, x) \\
 h(S(0), S(x)) \rightarrow \tilde{h}(x, x) & \tilde{h}(S(0), S(x)) \rightarrow h(x, x) \\
 h(S(S(x)), S(y)) \rightarrow h(x, y) & \tilde{h}(S(S(x)), S(y)) \rightarrow \tilde{h}(x, y)
 \end{array}$$

429 The n -th element T_n of T is defined by the recurrence:

$$430 \quad T_0 = 0 \quad T_{2n} = T_n \quad T_{2n+1} = 1 - T_n$$

431 Identifying natural numbers with their representations in the TRS, it may be shown by
 432 induction on $\langle 2m - n, n \rangle$ ordered lexicographically that the data term $h(n, m)$ reduces
 433 to T_{2m-n} and $\tilde{h}(n, m)$ to $1 - T_{2m-n}$.

434 5 Finite Stream Transducers

435 In this section we characterise the classes of stream functions computable by (jumping) finite
 436 stream transducers. In short, pure stream TRSs characterise the class of stream functions
 437 computable by jumping finite transducers, and right-linear pure stream TRSs characterise
 438 the class of stream functions computable by finite transducers. We first recall the definitions
 439 of (jumping) finite transducers from [14, 13].

440 ► **Definition 5.1.** An n -ary *jumping finite transducer* (JFT) over Σ -streams with m cursors is
 441 a tuple $\langle Q, q_0, C, \gamma, \delta \rangle$ where Q is a finite set of states, q_0 is the start state, $C = \{c_1, \dots, c_m\}$
 442 is the set of cursors, $\gamma : C \rightarrow \{1, \dots, n\}$ is the initial cursor configuration, and

$$443 \quad \delta : Q \times \Sigma^m \rightarrow Q \times (C \rightarrow C \cup \{+\}) \times (\Sigma \cup \{\epsilon\})$$

444 is the transition function. Intuitively, $\delta(q, \sigma_1, \dots, \sigma_m)$ consists of the next state, an indication
 445 of cursor movement, and an optional output symbol. A cursor may either move forward or
 446 jump to the position of another cursor. In other words, an n -ary JFT is a finite automaton
 447 with n read-only input tapes and one write-only output tape, and m cursors which can move
 448 forward on the input tapes and jump to positions of other cursors, but cannot be compared.

449 A *finite transducer* (FT) is a JFT such that no cursor ever jumps to the position of
 450 another (except to itself, which is equivalent to not moving). A *configuration* of a JFT
 451 consists of a state and a function $\pi : C \rightarrow \{1, \dots, n\} \times \mathbb{N}$ which assigns to each cursor c a
 452 stream index $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$ and a position in the stream. The *successor configuration* K' of
 453 a configuration K is determined in the obvious way by the transition function δ . The *initial*
 454 *configuration* is $\langle q_0, \pi_0 \rangle$ where $\pi_0(c) = \langle \gamma(c), 0 \rangle$ for $c \in C$. A *run* of a JFT $\langle Q, q_0, C, \gamma, \delta \rangle$ is
 455 an infinite sequence of configurations K_0, K_1, K_2, \dots such that K_0 is the initial configuration
 456 and K_{n+1} is the successor configuration of K_n for each $n \in \mathbb{N}$. The function $F : (\Sigma^\omega)^n \rightarrow \Sigma^{\leq \omega}$
 457 *computed* by a given n -ary FT (JFT) is defined in an obvious way, with $F(w_1, \dots, w_n)$ being
 458 the output of the transducer on inputs w_1, \dots, w_n . The output may be finite, because the
 459 transducer may loop.

460 ► **Theorem 5.2.** *An n -ary stream function is definable in a pure stream TRS with maximum*
 461 *function symbol arity m iff it is computable by an n -ary JFT with m cursors.*

462 **Proof.** Let $\langle Q, q_0, C, \gamma, \delta \rangle$ be an n -ary JFT with m cursors. Without loss of generality
 463 $C = \{1, \dots, m\}$. In the TRS we have a stream function symbol $f_q : s^m \rightarrow s$ for each state
 464 $q \in Q$. There is also the “start” stream function symbol $g : s^n \rightarrow s$. We have the rules e.g.

$$465 \quad f_q(\sigma_1 :: x_1, \dots, \sigma_m :: x_m) \rightarrow \sigma :: f_{q'}(\sigma_{\rho(1)} :: x_{\rho(1)}, x_2, \sigma_{\rho(3)} :: x_{\rho(3)}, \dots)$$

466 when $\delta(q, \sigma_1, \dots, \sigma_m) = \langle q', \rho, \sigma \rangle$ and $\rho(1), \rho(3), \dots \in C$ and $\rho(2) = +$. Intuitively, the
 467 arguments of f_q encode the m cursors. We also have the “start” rule:

$$468 \quad g(x_1, \dots, x_n) \rightarrow f_{q_0}(x_{\gamma(1)}, \dots, x_{\gamma(n)}).$$

469 Note that all of the above rules are simple stream rules and the TRS is orthogonal, so it
 470 is a pure stream TRS. It is easy to see that for each $s_1, \dots, s_n \in \mathcal{S}(\Sigma)$ there is a bijective
 471 correspondence between the infinite runs of the JFT on $|s_1|, \dots, |s_n|$ and infinite reductions
 472 starting at $g(s_1, \dots, s_n)$. This implies that the function defined by g is the same as the
 473 function computed by the JFT.

474 For the other direction, let R be a pure stream TRS with maximum function symbol
 475 arity m , and let the n -ary symbol g define a function $F : (\Sigma^\omega)^n \rightarrow \Sigma^{\leq \omega}$ where Σ is the set of
 476 data constants in R . We construct an n -ary JFT with m cursors.

477 Because there are no data rules or data constructors of arity > 0 , each rule is a simple
 478 stream rule of the form e.g.

$$479 \quad f(a :: u :: b :: x, a :: y, c) \rightarrow d :: g(u :: b :: x, e)$$

480 where $a, b, c, d, e \in \Sigma$, and u is a data variable. We will encode stream function symbols by
 481 (possibly many) states. Stream arguments will correspond to cursor positions.

482 Let N be the maximum size of the left-hand side l of a rule $l \rightarrow r \in R$. For a function
 483 symbol f with k stream and j data arguments, and words $w_1, \dots, w_k \in \Sigma^N$, and constants
 484 $c_1, \dots, c_j \in \Sigma$, we add a state $q_f^{w_1, \dots, w_k, c_1, \dots, c_j}$. The words w_1, \dots, w_k buffer the last N
 485 symbols read from each of the cursors. Let s_i be a stream term representing the word w_i ,
 486 with a variable x_i at the tail, e.g., if $w_i = abc$ then $s_i = a :: b :: c :: x_i$. Without loss of

487 generality assume the stream arguments of f occur before the data arguments. Because R is
 488 orthogonal, there is at most one rule $l \rightarrow r \in R$ such that l matches $f(s_1, \dots, s_k, c_1, \dots, c_j)$
 489 with some substitution σ , i.e., $\sigma l = f(s_1, \dots, s_k, c_1, \dots, c_j)$. Note that because of the choice
 490 of N , if there is no rule $l \rightarrow r \in R$ with l matching $f(s_1, \dots, s_k, c_1, \dots, c_j)$, then no left-hand
 491 side of a rule unifies with $f(s_1, \dots, s_k, c_1, \dots, c_j)$. Assume e.g.

$$492 \quad \sigma l = f(a :: b :: x, c :: d :: y, c_1)$$

493 and

$$494 \quad \sigma r = d :: g(c :: d :: y, b :: x, d :: y, c).$$

495 Then in the state q_f^{ab,cd,c_1} the JFT outputs d and simultaneously sets the first cursor to the
 496 second one, the second to the first, and the third to the second. Then it reads one symbol
 497 from the second cursor and one from the third, moving them forward. Let the read symbols
 498 be a_1, a_2 respectively. The JFT then enters the state $q_g^{cd,ba_1,da_2,c}$. This behaviour may always
 499 be encoded using a finite number of states.

500 The JFT starts in a state q_0 with the i -th cursor initialised to the beginning of the i -th
 501 input tape, for $i = 1, \dots, n$, and other cursors initialised arbitrarily. Then the JFT reads N
 502 symbols from each of the n input tapes, and reaches the state $q_g^{w_1, \dots, w_n}$ where $w_i \in \Sigma^N$ is
 503 the word consisting of the symbols read from the i -th input tape.

504 We also add a “trash” state q_T and add appropriate transitions to q_T from other states
 505 to make δ a total function.

506 For any $s_1, \dots, s_n \in \mathcal{S}(\Sigma)$ there is a bijective correspondence between the runs of the
 507 JFT on $|s_1|, \dots, |s_n|$ and the infinite reductions starting at $g(s_1, \dots, s_n)$, and the function
 508 computed by the JFT is the same as the function defined by g . ◀

509 ▶ **Theorem 5.3.** *An n -ary stream function is definable in a right-linear pure stream TRS*
 510 *with maximum function symbol arity m iff it is computable by an n -ary FT with m cursors.*

511 **Proof.** An adaptation of the proof of Theorem 5.2. More details are in Appendix B. ◀

512 **6 LOGSPACE for streams**

513 In this section we show that stream functions definable in simple stream TRSs are exactly
 514 the stream functions computable in LOGSPACE as defined by Ramyaa and Leivant [14, 13].
 515 First, we recall the definition of jumping Turing transducers from [14].

516 ▶ **Definition 6.1.** *A jumping Turing transducer (JTT) is defined analogously to a JFT,*
 517 *except that it has additional read-write work tapes with two-way cursors on them. The*
 518 *function computed by a JTT is defined in an obvious way. A JTT operates in space $f(n)$ if*
 519 *the computation for the first n output symbols does not involve work-tapes of length $> f(n)$.*
 520 *A stream function is computable in LOGSPACE if there is a JTT computing this function*
 521 *which operates in space $O(\log n)$.*

522 Note that the space used by a JTT is defined in terms of the output. Time restrictions
 523 defined in terms of the output do not make much sense for JTTs, because even for FTs no
 524 restriction is placed on how long it takes to output the next symbol (e.g. consider an FT
 525 over binary streams skipping all zeros and copying all ones).

526 We will show that JTTs operating in LOGSPACE compute exactly the stream functions
 527 definable in simple stream TRSs. First, we generalise eager $R\perp$ -reduction from Section 3 to
 528 stream TRSs.

529 ► **Definition 6.2.** Let \perp be a fresh nullary data constructor. We define the relation \rightarrow_{\perp}
 530 by: $t \rightarrow_{\perp} \perp$ if t is a data term and it does not R -reduce to a constructor normal form. We
 531 set $\rightarrow_{R\perp} = \rightarrow_R \cup \rightarrow_{\perp}$. A finitary $R\perp$ -reduction is *eager* if only innermost $R\perp$ -redexes are
 532 contracted and priority is given to \perp -reduction. We denote one-step eager $R\perp$ -reduction
 533 by $\rightarrow_{R\perp e}$. The relation $\rightarrow_{R\perp e}^{\infty}$ of *infinitary eager $R\perp$ -reduction* is defined coinductively.

$$534 \frac{t \rightarrow_{R\perp e}^* t' \quad t \rightarrow_{R\perp e}^* u :: w \quad w \rightarrow_{R\perp e}^{\infty} w'}{t \rightarrow_{R\perp e}^{\infty} t' \quad t \rightarrow_{R\perp e}^{\infty} u :: w'}$$

535 Because of space limits, the proofs of lemmas concerning infinitary eager $R\perp$ -reduction
 536 are delegated to Appendix C.

537 *In the rest of this section we assume R to be a simple stream TRS.*

538 ► **Definition 6.3.** A term is *proper* if all its data subterms are finite.

539 If t is proper and $t \rightarrow_R t'$ then t' is also proper, because R is finite.

540 ► **Lemma 6.4.** *If t is proper and $t \rightarrow_R^{\infty} t_1$ and $t \rightarrow_{R\perp e}^{\infty} t_2$ then there is t' with $t_2 \rightarrow_R^{\infty} t'$ and*
 541 *$t_1 \rightarrow_{R\perp e}^{\infty} t_2$.*

542 ► **Lemma 6.5.** *If $s \in \mathcal{S}^+(\Sigma)$ and $s \rightarrow_{R\perp e}^{\infty} s'$ (resp. $s \rightarrow_R^{\infty} s'$), then $s \sim s'$ and $s' \in \mathcal{S}^+(\Sigma)$.*

543 ► **Theorem 6.6.** *If a stream function is definable in a simple stream TRS then it is computable*
 544 *in LOGSPACE.*

545 **Proof.** Let $F : (\Sigma^{\omega})^n \rightarrow \Sigma^{\leq \omega}$ be a function defined by an n -ary stream function symbol f_0 in
 546 a simple stream TRS R , i.e., a finite orthogonal data tail-recursive stream TRS with simple
 547 stream rules and simple data. We describe how to construct a JTT operating in LOGSPACE
 548 which computes F .

549 For $s_1, \dots, s_n \in \mathcal{S}(\Sigma)$ we have $f_0(s_1, \dots, s_n) \rightarrow_R^{\infty} s \in \mathcal{S}^+(\Sigma)$ where $F(|s_1|, \dots, |s_n|) = |s|$.
 550 The constructed JTT will essentially compute an $s' \in \mathcal{S}^+(\Sigma)$ such that $f_0(s_1, \dots, s_n) \rightarrow_{R\perp e}^{\infty} s'$,
 551 for a certain fixed infinitary eager $R\perp$ -reduction. By Lemma 6.4 and Lemma 6.5 we then
 552 have $|s| = |s'|$.

553 Note that because the TRS is finite and has simple data, all constructor normal form
 554 data terms occurring in any reduction $f_0(s_1, \dots, s_n) \rightarrow_{R\perp e}^{\infty} s$ have the form $S^m(t)$ where
 555 either $t \in \Sigma$ or it is one of the finitely many constructor normal form data terms occurring in
 556 the right-hand sides of the stream or data rules. Because S cannot occur in the right-hand side
 557 of a simple stream rule if no stream element is produced, and data rules are cons-free, m is at
 558 most proportional to the number of output stream elements already produced. Hence $S^m(t)$
 559 may be represented in logspace, using a logarithmic counter for m and a constant number
 560 of bits to represent t . Because the reduction is eager and the size of right-hand sides of
 561 stream rules is bounded by a constant, using an analogon of Proposition 3.17 we obtain
 562 a JTT which computes in logarithmic space the constructor normal form of a given data
 563 term occurring in the reduction, if it has one. This JTT computes the constructor normal
 564 forms “inside-out”. For a term $f(t_1, \dots, t_k)$ first the constructor normal forms t'_1, \dots, t'_k
 565 are computed. Each t'_i has the form $S^{m_i}(u'_i)$ where u'_i is either \perp or one of the finitely
 566 many constructor normal forms occurring in the right-hand sides of the rules. Then using
 567 (an analogon of) Proposition 3.17 we compute the constructor normal form of $f(t'_1, \dots, t'_k)$.
 568 For $S(t)$ first the constructor normal form $S^m(t')$ of t is computed using Proposition 3.17, and
 569 then $S^{m+1}(t')$ is returned as the constructor normal form of t . Note that the only property
 570 the constructor normal forms needed in Proposition 3.17 is that they can be represented

571 using a logarithmic number of bits, and given a representation of $S(t)$ the representation of t
 572 may be computed in logarithmic space.

573 We construct the JTT like in Theorem 5.2, except that now the data arguments are
 574 stored in memory instead of the state. We compute constructor normal forms of data terms
 575 using Proposition 3.17. This is done eagerly, before transitioning to the state associated
 576 with the stream function symbol in the right-hand side, which ensures that the size of the
 577 “prefix” containing all defined function symbols of each data term occurring in the reduction
 578 is constant – it is bounded by the size of the right-hand side of a rule in R . More details are
 579 in Appendix C. ◀

580 ▶ **Theorem 6.7.** *If a stream function is computable in LOGSPACE then it is definable in a*
 581 *simple stream TRS.*

582 **Proof.** Let $F : (\Sigma^\omega)^n \rightarrow \Sigma^{\leq\omega}$ be a function computed by a JTT operating in LOGSPACE.
 583 As shown in [14, Proposition 2.4], the function F is also computed by a JFT with a local
 584 counter, i.e., a JFT with an additional input tape which contains 1^n when computing the
 585 n -th output symbol. In other words, a 1 is appended to the local counter whenever a symbol
 586 is output by the JFT. Initially, the local counter contains the empty word. The JFT has a
 587 fixed number of cursors on the local counter, which are reset to the beginning of the local
 588 counter tape whenever a symbol is output. As with the cursors on the input, the cursors
 589 on the local counter may move to the right or jump to other cursors. Hence, they may be
 590 encoded in an analogous way as the cursors on the input stream.

591 A simple stream TRS defining a function computed by a JFT with a local counter may
 592 be constructed in a way analogous to the construction of a pure stream TRS in the proof
 593 of Theorem 5.2. The difference is that now every function symbol f_q corresponding to a
 594 state q has an additional data argument representing the local counter, and data arguments
 595 encoding the cursors on the local counter. The local counter contents 1^n is represented by
 596 the data term $S^n(0)$, where $S : d \rightarrow d$ and $0 : d$. If a rule associated with f_q produces a new
 597 output symbol, then in the right-hand side of the rule the local counter is “increased” by
 598 prepending S , and the data arguments encoding cursors on the local counter are set to the
 599 local counter. This may be encoded in a simple stream rule. The resulting stream TRS has
 600 simple data.

601 Note that the constructed simple stream TRS actually has no data rules. It is not a pure
 602 stream TRS because it has a unary data constructor S . ◀

603 ▶ **Corollary 6.8.** *A stream function is computable in LOGSPACE iff it is definable in a*
 604 *simple stream TRS.*

605 7 Conclusions

606 We have shown an infinitary rewriting characterisation of LOGSPACE-computable stream
 607 functions as defined by Ramyaa and Leivant. In the realm of finite data, we proved that
 608 finite orthogonal tail-recursive cons-free constructor TRSs characterise LOGSPACE.

609 Our proof could probably be adapted to show that finite semi-linear [10] tail-recursive
 610 cons-free constructor TRSs characterise NLOGSPACE. In the nondeterministic case the
 611 trick with logarithmic counters is not necessary as the procedure may simply guess when to
 612 contract a subterm to \perp . Semi-linearity ensures that subterms containing redexes cannot get
 613 duplicated, which is crucial to show that a constructor normal form may always be reached
 614 via an eager $R\perp$ -reduction.

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A Confluence of infinitary reduction

644

645

► **Lemma A.1.** *If $t \rightarrow_R^\infty t' \rightarrow_R^* t''$ then $t \rightarrow_R^\infty t''$.*

646

647

648

Proof. By coinduction. If $t \rightarrow_R^* t'$ then this is obvious. Otherwise $t' = u :: w'$ and $t \rightarrow_R^* u :: w$ and $w \rightarrow_R^\infty w'$ and $t'' = u'' :: w''$ and $u \rightarrow_R^* u''$ and $w' \rightarrow_R^* w''$. Then $t \rightarrow_R^* u'' :: w$. By coinduction also $w \rightarrow_R^\infty w''$. Hence $t \rightarrow_R^\infty u'' :: w'' = t''$. ◀

649

► **Lemma A.2.** *If $t \rightarrow_R^\infty t' \rightarrow_R^\infty t''$ then $t \rightarrow_R^\infty t''$.*

650

Proof. By coinduction, using Lemma A.1. ◀

651

652

► **Lemma A.3.** *Let R be finite and orthogonal. If $t \rightarrow_R^\infty t'$ and $t \rightarrow_R^* s$ then there is s' with $s \rightarrow_R^\infty s'$ and $t' \rightarrow_R^\infty s'$.*

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654

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657

Proof. By coinduction, analysing $t \rightarrow_R^\infty t'$. If $t \rightarrow_R^* t'$ then this follows from Lemma 4.4. Otherwise $t' = u :: w'$, and $t \rightarrow_R^* u :: w$ and $w \rightarrow_R^\infty w'$. By Lemma 4.4 there are u_1, w_1 such that $s \rightarrow_R^* u_1 :: w_1$ and $u \rightarrow_R^* u_1$ and $w \rightarrow_R^* w_1$. By coinduction we obtain w_2 with $w_1 \rightarrow_R^\infty w_2$ and $w' \rightarrow_R^\infty w_2$. Hence $s \rightarrow_R^\infty u_1 :: w_2$, because $s \rightarrow_R^* u_1 :: w_1$ and $w_1 \rightarrow_R^\infty w_2$; and $t' \rightarrow_R^\infty u_1 :: w_2$, because $t' = u :: w' \rightarrow_R^* u_1 :: w'$ and $w' \rightarrow_R^\infty w_2$. ◀

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660

Note that $t' \rightarrow_R^* s'$ would not suffice in the conclusion of the above lemma, because the infinitary reduction $t \rightarrow_R^\infty t'$ may create in t' infinitely many descendants of a redex in t .

The relation $\rightarrow_R^{2\infty}$ is defined coinductively.

661

$$\frac{t \rightarrow_R^\infty t' \quad t \rightarrow_R^\infty u :: w \quad w \rightarrow_R^{2\infty} w'}{t \rightarrow_R^{2\infty} t' \quad t \rightarrow_R^{2\infty} u :: w'}$$

662

► **Lemma A.4.** *If $t \rightarrow_R^\infty t' \rightarrow_R^{2\infty} t''$ then $t \rightarrow_R^{2\infty} t''$.*

663

Proof. Follows directly from Lemma A.2 ◀

664

► **Lemma A.5.** *If $t \rightarrow_R^{2\infty} t'$ then $t \rightarrow_R^\infty t'$.*

665

Proof. By coinduction, using Lemma A.4. ◀

■ **Figure 1** Proof of confluence of infinitary reduction

666

667

► **Theorem 4.5.** *If R is finite and orthogonal then \rightarrow_R^∞ is confluent, i.e., if $t \rightarrow_R^\infty t_1$ and $t \rightarrow_R^\infty t_2$ then there exists t' such that $t_1 \rightarrow_R^\infty t'$ and $t_2 \rightarrow_R^\infty t'$.*

668 **Proof.** By coinduction we construct t' such that $t_1 \rightarrow_R^{2\infty} t'$ and $t_2 \rightarrow_R^{2\infty} t'$. This suffices by
 669 Lemma A.5. If $t \rightarrow_R^* t_1$ or $t \rightarrow_R^* t_2$ then the claim follows from Lemma A.3. Otherwise,
 670 $t_i = u_i :: w'_i$ and $t \rightarrow_R^* u_i :: w_i$ and $w_i \rightarrow_R^\infty w'_i$ for $i = 1, 2$. By Lemma 4.4 there are u, w such
 671 that $u_i \rightarrow_R^* u$ and $w_i \rightarrow_R^* w$. By Lemma A.3 there are w'_1, w'_2 such that $w'_i \rightarrow_R^\infty w''_i$ and
 672 $w \rightarrow_R^\infty w''$. Hence $t_i = u_i :: w'_i \rightarrow_R^\infty u :: w''_i$. By coinduction we obtain w' with $w'_i \rightarrow_R^{2\infty} w'$.
 673 Thus $t_i \rightarrow_R^{2\infty} u :: w'$, so we may take $t' = u :: w'$. See Figure 1. ◀

674 B Characterisation of Finite Stream Transducers

675 ▶ **Theorem 5.3.** *An n -ary stream function is definable in a right-linear pure stream TRS*
 676 *with maximum function symbol arity m iff it is computable by an n -ary FT with m cursors.*

677 **Proof.** First note that for an FT the construction of a stream TRS in the proof of Theorem 5.2
 678 gives a right-linear system. Conversely, if the TRS is right-linear, then we may modify the
 679 construction of a JFT in the proof of Theorem 5.2 to obtain an FT, by keeping in the
 680 state the information which cursor a given function argument corresponds to. So a state
 681 corresponding to a function symbol f is now $q_f^{w_1, \dots, w_k, c_1, \dots, c_j, i_1, \dots, i_k}$ where i_1, \dots, i_k indicate
 682 the cursors corresponding to the stream arguments of f . For instance, if

$$683 \quad \sigma l = f(a :: b :: x, c :: d :: y, c_1)$$

684 and

$$685 \quad \sigma r = d :: h(c :: d :: y, b :: x, c)$$

686 then the transition from the state $q_f^{ab, cd, c_1, i_1, i_2}$ is constructed as follows. First, output d
 687 and read one symbol e from the i_1 -th cursor moving it forward. Then change the state
 688 to $q_h^{cd, be, c, i_2, i_1}$. ◀

689 C Proofs for Section 6

690 In this section we assume that R is a simple stream TRS.

691 ▶ **Lemma C.1.** *If t is proper and $t \rightarrow_R^\infty t_1$ and $t \rightarrow_{R \perp e}^* t_2$ then there is t' with $t_2 \rightarrow_R^\infty t'$ and*
 692 *$t_1 \rightarrow_{R \perp e}^\infty t_2$.*

693 **Proof.** By coinduction, analysing $t \rightarrow_R^\infty t_1$. If $t \rightarrow_R^* t_1$ then this follows from Corollary 3.15.
 694 Otherwise $t \rightarrow_R^* u :: w$ and $w \rightarrow_R^\infty w'$ and $t_1 = u :: w'$. By Corollary 3.15 there are u_2, w_2
 695 with $t_2 \rightarrow_R^* u_2 :: w_2$ and $u \rightarrow_{R \perp e}^* u_2$ and $w \rightarrow_{R \perp e}^* w_2$. Note that w is proper. By coinduction
 696 we obtain w'_2 with $w_2 \rightarrow_R^\infty w'_2$ and $w' \rightarrow_{R \perp e}^\infty w'_2$. Take $t' = u_2 :: w'_2$. We have $t_2 \rightarrow_R^* u_2 :: w_2$
 697 and $w_2 \rightarrow_R^\infty w'_2$, so $t_2 \rightarrow_R^\infty t'$. Also $t_1 = u :: w' \rightarrow_{R \perp e}^* u_2 :: w'$ and $w' \rightarrow_{R \perp e}^\infty w'_2$, so
 698 $t_1 \rightarrow_{R \perp e}^\infty t'$. ◀

699 ▶ **Lemma 6.4.** *If t is proper and $t \rightarrow_R^\infty t_1$ and $t \rightarrow_{R \perp e}^\infty t_2$ then there is t' with $t_2 \rightarrow_R^\infty t'$ and*
 700 *$t_1 \rightarrow_{R \perp e}^\infty t_2$.*

701 **Proof.** By coinduction, analysing $t \rightarrow_{R \perp e}^\infty t_2$. If $t \rightarrow_{R \perp e}^* t_2$ then this is a consequence of
 702 Lemma C.1. Otherwise $t \rightarrow_{R \perp e}^* u :: w$ and $w \rightarrow_{R \perp e}^\infty w'$ and $t_2 = u :: w'$. By Lemma C.1 there
 703 are u_1, w_1 such that $t_1 \rightarrow_{R \perp e}^* u_1 :: w_1$ and $u \rightarrow_R^* u_1$ and $w \rightarrow_R^\infty w_1$. Note that w is proper.
 704 By coinduction we obtain w_2 such that $w' \rightarrow_R^\infty w_2$ and $w_1 \rightarrow_{R \perp e}^\infty w_2$. Take $t' = u_1 :: w_2$. We
 705 have $t_1 \rightarrow_{R \perp e}^* u_1 :: w_1$ and $w_1 \rightarrow_{R \perp e}^\infty w_2$, so $t_1 \rightarrow_{R \perp e}^\infty t'$. Also $t_2 = u :: w' \rightarrow_R^* u_1 :: w'$ and
 706 $w' \rightarrow_R^\infty w_2$, so $t_2 \rightarrow_R^\infty t'$. ◀

707 ▶ **Lemma C.2.** *If $t \rightarrow_{R\perp}^* u :: w$ then t has a chnf (in R).*

708 **Proof.** Induction on the number of \perp -reduction steps in $t \rightarrow_{R\perp}^* u :: w$. If there are none
 709 then $t \rightarrow_R^* u :: w$. Otherwise by the inductive hypothesis $t \rightarrow_R^* t' \rightarrow_{\perp} t'' \rightarrow_R^* u' :: w'$.
 710 Because R is finite, by the same argument as in the proof of Lemma 3.4 we conclude that
 711 $t \rightarrow_R^* t' \rightarrow_R^* u'' :: w'' \rightarrow_{\perp}^* u' :: w'$. ◀

712 ▶ **Lemma 6.5.** *If $s \in \mathcal{S}^+(\Sigma)$ and $s \rightarrow_{R\perp e}^{\infty} s'$ (resp. $s \rightarrow_R^{\infty} s'$), then $s \sim s'$ and $s' \in \mathcal{S}^+(\Sigma)$.*

713 **Proof.** It suffices to notice that if t is a stream term without a chnf and $t \rightarrow_{R\perp e}^{\infty} t'$ (resp. $t \rightarrow_R^{\infty}$
 714 t') then t' does not have a chnf either. This follows from Lemma C.2 (resp. Lemma 4.6). ◀

715 ▶ **Theorem 6.6.** *If a stream function is definable in a simple stream TRS then it is computable
 716 in LOGSPACE.*

717 **Proof.** We describe in more detail the construction of a JTT already sketched in Section 6.
 718 The constructed JTT computes the stream $c_1 :: c_2 :: c_3 :: \dots$ where e.g.

$$719 \quad f_0(s_1, \dots, s_n) \rightarrow_R^{\epsilon} t_1 :: f_1(w_1^1, \dots, w_{k_1}^1) \rightarrow_{R\perp e}^* c_1 :: f_1(u_1^1, \dots, u_{k_1}^1) \rightarrow_R^{\epsilon} \\ c_1 :: t_2 :: t_3 :: f_2(w_1^2, \dots, w_{k_2}^2) \rightarrow_{R\perp e}^* c_1 :: c_2 :: c_3 :: f_2(u_1^1, \dots, u_{k_2}^1) \rightarrow_R^{\epsilon} \dots$$

720 and none of the u_i^j contain $R\perp$ -redexes. So all of the root R -reduction steps are in fact eager
 721 $R\perp$ -reductions. Note that all terms appearing in this reduction are proper.

722 Let N be the maximum size of the left-hand side l of a rule $l \rightarrow r \in R$. For a
 723 stream function symbol f with k stream arguments, and words $w_1, \dots, w_k \in \Sigma^N$ we add a
 724 state $q_f^{w_1, \dots, w_k}$. Let s_i be a stream term representing the word w_i , with a variable x_i at the
 725 tail, like in the proof of Theorem 5.2. Assume without loss of generality that the stream
 726 arguments of f occur before the data arguments, and let y_1, \dots, y_j be data variables. Let
 727 $l_1 \rightarrow r_1, \dots, l_n \rightarrow r_n \in R$ be all rules such that $f(s_1, \dots, s_k, y_1, \dots, y_j)$ unifies with l_i with
 728 substitution σ_i . Let M be the maximum number of data arguments of any defined stream
 729 function symbol in R . We keep the representations of data arguments in constructor normal
 730 form on M separate work tapes: we call them argument work tapes.

731 Assume e.g. $k = 2$ and $w_1 = ab$ and $w_2 = cd$ and $j = 2$. In the state $q_f^{ab, cd}$ the JTT
 732 first checks which of the left-hand sides l_1, \dots, l_n matches $f(a :: b :: x_1, c :: d :: x_2, u_1, u_2)$
 733 where u is the first data argument – the data term whose representation is stored on the
 734 first argument work tape. There is at most one matching l_i because R is orthogonal, and
 735 this can be checked using only logarithmic space (it suffices to check whether the two data
 736 arguments in l_i match u_1, u_2 , respectively). If none of the l_i matches then the JTT loops.
 737 Assume e.g. l_i matches with substitution σ and

$$738 \quad \sigma l_i = f(a :: b :: x_1, c :: d :: x_2, S(y), z)$$

739 and

$$740 \quad \sigma r_i = h_1(a, b, y, z) :: g(c :: d :: x_2, b :: x_1, d :: x_2, h_2(y), y).$$

741 Then the JTT outputs the constructor normal form of $h_1(a, b, t_1, t_2)$, computed using
 742 Proposition 3.17, where $S(t_1)$ is the constructor normal form of the first data argument,
 743 stored on the first argument work tape, and t_2 is the constructor normal form of the second
 744 data argument, stored on the second argument work tape. If the constructor normal form
 745 of $h_1(a, b, t_1, t_2)$ is not in Σ , then the JTT loops. Next, the JTT simultaneously sets the
 746 first cursor to the second one, the second to the first, and the third to the second. Then it

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747 computes the constructor normal form of $h_2(t)$, using Proposition 3.17, and writes it to the
748 first argument tape, and also copies t to the second argument tape. Next, the JTT reads
749 one symbol from the second cursor and one from the third, moving them forward. Let these
750 symbols be a_1, a_2 respectively. The JTT then enters the state q_g^{cd,ba_1,da_2} . This behaviour
751 may always be encoded using a finite number of states.

752 The rest of the construction is like in the proof of Theorem 5.2.

753 It is clear that the constructed JTT computes a stream $|s'| \in \Sigma^{\leq \omega}$ for an $s' \in \mathcal{S}^+(\Sigma)$
754 such that $f_0(s_1, \dots, s_n) \rightarrow_{R \perp e}^\infty s'$. As mentioned before, Lemma 6.4 and Lemma 6.5 imply
755 that this is correct. Indeed, we have $f_0(s_1, \dots, s_n) \rightarrow_R^\infty s$ where $F(|s_1|, \dots, |s_n|) = |s|$. By
756 Lemma 6.4 there is w with $s \rightarrow_{R \perp e}^\infty w$ and $s' \rightarrow_R^\infty w$. By Lemma 6.5 we have $w \in \mathcal{S}^+(\Sigma)$
757 and $s \sim w$ and $s' \sim w$. Thus $|s| = |w| = |s'|$. So the JTT computes the stream $|s|$, as
758 required. ◀